

Crop management

Low-tillage broadcast rice productivity

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Rice - rice - green manure is a primary cropping pattern in Hunan Province. In general, a field must be plowed and harrowed several times a year. That destroys the soil structure, results in poorer soil aeration, demands more labor, and risks seedling damage from low temperature in May or high temperature in Jul.

Table 2. Rice benefits from 2 cultivation methods. Changsha, China, 1986.

Treatment	Rice season	Yield (t/ha)	Output value ^a (\$/ha)	Cost (\$/ha)	Net income (\$/ha)	Income increase (%)	Labor days/ha	Income/labor day (\$)	Income increase (%)
Low tillage, broadcast	Apr - Oct	13.9	1450.46	535.93	914.87	30.16	233	3.94	90
Transplanted	Apr - Oct	11.8	1235.19	532.30	702.89	—	339	2.07	—
Low tillage, broadcast	Jun - Oct	8.5	885.12	261.20	623.92	30.76	120	5.20	96
Transplanted	Jun - Oct	7.3	760.76	283.62	477.14	—	180	2.65	—

^aRice price US\$104.50/t (local government price). Exchange rate: US\$100 = 371.27 yuan RMB.

To maintain soil productivity and high rice yields, we developed a minimum tillage and broadcast sowing rice cultivation method. Experiments to study the economic benefits and effects on soil structure between the new

method and conventional transplanting began in 1983.

Our results show that the new method has a significant effect on rice yield and economic return (Table 1, 2). □

Table 1. Rice yield from 2 cultivation methods. Changsha, China, 1984-87.

Location	Cropping pattern	Season	Rice variety	Yield (t/ha)		Yield increase (%)
				Low tillage broadcast	Transplanted	
Changsha	Green manure - rice	Apr ^a - Jul	1984 Zhefur 802	6.8	5.9	15.2
Nan County	Fallow - rice	Apr - Jul	78-1000	7.3	6.0	22
Changsha	Green manure - rice	Apr - Jul	1985 Xiangzhao xieng 3	6.2	5.8	7
Changsha	Green manure - rice - rice	Apr ^b - Oct	Zhefu 802-V35	14.4	13.8	5
Nan County	Green manure - rice - rice	Apr - Oct	Zhaoyun fong-V35	13.7	12.3	11
Changsha	Green manure - rice	Apr - Jul	1986 2106	5.6	5.4	4
Changsha	Green manure - rice	Apr - Jul	1987 V35	6.3	4.8	32
Changsha	Barley - rice	Apr - Jul	V35	6.6	6.2	5

^aOne crop season. ^bTwo crop seasons.

Disease management

Host plants of rice tungro (RTV)-associated viruses

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In previous studies on RTV hosts, inoculated weed plants were indexed on the basis of infection and by testing

transmission of infection from weeds to rice by the vector green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. Results were contradictory.

This study had two treatments. In the first, young seedlings of 5 *Oryza* spp. and 19 weed species were inoculated separately by exposing each seedling for 1 d to 10 GLH that had fed for 4 d on plants infected with both rice tungro bacilliform (RTRV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses. In the second treatment, seedlings of 4 *Oryza* spp. and 19 weed species were inoculated with

GLH that had fed on RTSV-infected plants.

At 30 d after inoculation, plants were indexed by ELISA for the presence of RTBV and RTSV. Extracts of inoculated plants having absorbance at 405 nm 3 times higher than that of uninoculated plant extracts were considered to contain virus.

When seedlings were inoculated by GLH that had fed on plants infected with RTBV and RTSV, all *Oryza* spp. except *O. latifolia* were infected with RTBV and RTSV (Table 1). All doubly